

SOCIAL MOVEMENTS AND REVOLUTIONS

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1. INTRODUCTION

- **MOVEMENT:** Development and propagation of an innovative political, social, ideological and cultural trend.
- **REVOLUTION:** Violent change in the political institutions of a nation or new form in the state or in the government of things.

Disagreement with a certain order established at a given historical moment that is intended to change.

The science that is dedicated to its study and analysis is STASIOLOGY (stasis: standing up against something).

There are three large groups of movements in contemporary times:

- **MARGINAL MOVEMENTS:** Very violent movements, outbursts. Very rapid movements in their development, without a clear ideological base in some cases or in others with a primary, shallow character. They respond to circumstantial situations. They are usual movements in traditional societies. for example the peasant movements. Which continue to respond to some schemes, which have remained practically unchanged. They respond to conjunctural situations, alteration of their situation, pretending to restore the previously existing situation. Belonging to these movements we can also catalog the urban riots, which respond to the established criteria, seek to restore a certain balance, traditional societies in which situations of scarcity occur conjuncturally and therefore a sharp rise in the precise what in turn provokes a subsistence crisis. Finally, it is worth mentioning the wildcat strikes of paleoliberalism, which we can locate in pre-industrial English society. They are violent and rapid impulses, as is the case of the Luddite movement, which developed against the machines to restore a balance in which the basis of work was labor.
- **MOVEMENTS AGAINST SOCIETY:** They are not violent movements, or at least in their origin, and can become violent if they are harassed. They are long-term movements, with a precise ideology, which pose an alternative if not to the entire established order, yes to a certain aspect. These are groups or social sectors that do not agree with the current system or structure, trying to separate themselves from society, isolate themselves and therefore create their own society within it. As an example of these movements we find the sects or movements that act from within society but expressing their disagreement (mov. Pacifists -in its beginnings-, environmentalists, feminists or gangsters).
- **REVOLUTIONARY MOVEMENTS:** They are violent movements, with an ideological support based on their disagreement with the existing order. Neither the fringe movements nor the movements against society have any intention of reaching power. Revolutionary movements have as their great objective access to power, from there to modify the established order.

The rapid and profound changes that contemporary society has experienced are given by revolutionary movements in most cases.

THE OBJECT OF OUR ANALYSIS WILL BE THE REVOLUTIONARY MOVEMENTS AND THEIR IMPACT ON SOCIETY

• **PRIOR FRAMEWORK. THE ORDER ESTABLISHED:**

The revolutionary movements will rise up against the established order, therefore, it will be necessary to analyze the previous framework to understand these movements.

2. ANALYSIS VARIABLES

• Degree of immobility or innovation: an immobile system is more solid than an innovative system unless it is fully agreed upon by society.

• Degree of operability or lag of that order: An order that has been outdated does not respond to the needs of society, therefore, it will be less stable.

• Degree of pluralism or monopoly: a plural order, which responds or accommodates different sectors of society, will be more stable than one directed towards a specific sector or minority sectors.

• Degree of strength or weakness.

• Degree of concentration or dispersion: the more concentrated the order or power, the more solid the system will be.

• **REVOLUTIONARY FRAME:**

• **THE ROOT OF THE REVOLUTIONS:** any existing order in a specific place and time is the result of an established social consensus in which the citizens are in agreement with the established order - SOCIAL CONTRACT.

In any established order there is a certain hierarchy of values (religious base, social or economic values, etc.), there will be stability when there is an agreement with these values, so that institutions can be raised and therefore sustain the system. The root, therefore, is found in the fact that a sector of that community is not in accordance with the established order. But that hierarchy is arbitrary - elective. They choose, they decide. In this arbitrariness the values can be one or the other. One sector or several, can vary or change the values and lean towards another hierarchy. The consensus is broken.

Political representation, economic power, the power of institutions or social representation are goods in the hands of a certain sector, that is, they are scarce goods, in the hands of a few people. Those who disagree with the established order are those who want access to the new order and scarce goods. All revolutions, at least, originally seek to access equality.

El origen de la revolución esta en la ruptura de un contrato social, en su día aceptado, asentado en unos valores de origen electivo con el cual un sector de la población se encuentra en desacuerdo. Por lo tanto, el movimiento revolucionario pretende acceder a la igualdad inexistente debido a la escasez de ciertos bienes, los cuales son detentados por ciertos sectores pertenecientes a esa comunidad.

THE ORDER IS AGREED ON A SCALE OF VALUES.

• **THE MECHANICS OF REVOLUTIONS:** Movement whose main objective is to take power to modify the existing order and impose a new one based on a new hierarchy of values. There will inevitably be a confrontation between the established order and those who support it and the new or alternative order and those who identify themselves. A confrontation that is exclusive. Agreement or negotiation is not possible, it implies the use of violence, although there is no annihilation of society because there are a series of brakes that prevent reaching the ultimate consequences (number, material means or infrastructure, will, etc.) .

• **Number:** life in society supposes the existence of a contract signed by the majority of those who make it up. There may come a time when a certain group thinks that there is another scale of values and breaks that contract. The rest of the population continues to support that existing order. The number of people or sectors in principle will be more important among those who support the established order, being, therefore, smaller the number of those who support the new movement. This is the case on most occasions, although several exceptions can be made, it is about the great revolutionary processes, where the revolutionary sector is in the minority, what happens is that throughout the process there can be a tilt or change to favor of the revolutionaries (France in 1789 or Russia in 1917).

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- Material means: economic, military, communications infrastructure E.T.C. In principle they are controlled by the existing order, they constitute a brake that in principle is in favor of the established order.
- Will to win: The sector that represents the established order is more solid, strong and defined than the revolutionaries. In the sense that their economic, social, political, cultural and ideological survival is at stake and because whoever supports the established order is seeking their survival. On the revolutionary side there is an elite group fully imbued with ideas and aware of what they want. The support that this revolutionary sector can count on is much more hypothetical or relative than the previous one. In principle, all this tells us that, in theory, the established order has more guarantees of being maintained. It is not so easy to modify the existing order.

The objective of revolutions is the conservation of power or access to it. We can find ourselves in different situations but in any case we find ourselves with the restoration of power, implementation of a new order or conservation - maintenance of the existing order.

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